

MODERATING ROLE OF GROUP AFFILIATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FACEBOOK CONTENTS AND ELECTORATES' POLITICAL BEHAVIOUR IN NIGERIA'S 2023 PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION

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Abstract

The broad objective of this study was to investigate the moderating effect of group affiliation on the relationship between Facebook content and electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria. Specifically, the study sort to determine the extent to which: Facebook content influences the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria; and Group affiliations moderate the effect of Facebook content on the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria. Two hypotheses were formulated in line with the objectives of the study. A cross-sectional research design and survey method of data collection were adopted. The study covers the six geo-political zones in Nigeria in order to create a proper representation for the whole country. The following states were chosen to cover for each of the geo-political zones in Nigeria: Enugu (South-East), River (South-South), Abuja (North-Central), Lagos (South-West), Gombe (North-East), and Kano (North-West). The population of the study comprised of the 21,777,649 registered voters in these states. Applying the Taro Yamane formula, 400 electorates were selected using the stratified sampling technique. The instrument used in collecting data for this study was a five-point Likert scaled questionnaire administered online by means of Google form. The two hypotheses were tested at a 5% level of significance using the Regression statistics. The study's findings indicate that Facebook contents significantly and positively influenced electorates' political behaviour in the Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Election. The result further shows that moderating role of group affiliation was significant, suggesting that individuals' group identities shaped their responses to Facebook contents and political behaviour. This explains why there were so many contents on Facebook about the elections but the behaviour of the electorates didn't reflect it. The study contributes to understanding the complex dynamics of social media, group affiliation, and political behavior in Nigeria's democratic process.

Keywords: Group Affiliation, Social Media, Facebook Contents, Political Behaviour, Nigeria, Election.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have revolutionized how businesses communicate with their customers globally. Kaplan & Haenlein (2010) noted that the use of these technologies, particularly the social media, spans various fields, with evidence showing their widespread applications. In politics, for instance, the use of social media has grown considerably. Social media has transformed political marketing and how candidates interact with voters (Christine, 2017). This made social media, especially, Facebook to evolve from merely being a tool for political parties and candidates to market themselves and their ideas into a platform for mobilizing participation and educating the electorates about the political process as well as influencing their political behaviour.

Previous studies have shown that social media use is positively correlated with political participation, including voting, attending rallies, and engaging in online discussions (Gil de Zúñiga et al., 2012; Bond et al., 2012). Facebook, as a popular social media platform, has been used by politicians and electorates to share information, mobilize support, and engage in political discussions (Gerodimos & Justinussen, 2015).

Nowadays, the increasing penetration of social media has transformed the way people engage with politics in Nigeria (Adegbola & Olowookere, 2014). Facebook, in particular, has become a crucial platform for political discourse, mobilization, and participation (Okoro & Nwafor, 2013). The 2023 Presidential Election in Nigeria presented a unique opportunity to examine the role of Facebook in shaping electorates' political behavior.

The increasing influence of social media on political behaviour and democratic processes has raised concerns among scholars and practitioners alike. (Gil de Zúñiga et al., 2012). In Nigeria, the use of Facebook has become widespread, and its role in shaping electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 Presidential Election is significant (Adegbola & Olowookere, 2014).

Group affiliation, including party identification and membership in interest groups, can also influence political behaviour and attitudes (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; Brewer, 1999). In Nigeria, group affiliation may play a significant role in shaping electorates' responses to Facebook contents and political behaviour.

Sule, et. al (2017) identified sociological approach as one of the three major propositions to electorate political behavior in Nigeria. Others are identification model and rational choice. The sociological model postulates that political behaviour is as a result of the impact of social structure which indicates that social group membership influence electorate political behaviour (Daniel, 2015). This implies that most electorates will likely support a candidate that belongs to their social group. This explains why religious and ethnic groups as well as party membership have shown to dictate the pattern of voting (political behaviour) in Nigeria.

Despite the growing body of research on social media and politics, there is paucity of empirical studies on the moderating role of group affiliation on the relationship between Facebook contents and electorates' political behavior in Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Election. Hence, there is a gap in extant literature in understanding how group affiliation moderates the relationship between Facebook contents and electorates' political behaviour. This present study is poised to bridge this lacuna by investigating the moderating effect of group affiliation on the relationship between Facebook content and electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

Specifically, the study sort to determine the extent to which:

- 1 Facebook content influences the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.
- 2 Group affiliations moderate the effect of Facebook content on the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. Facebook content has no significant effect on the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.
2. Group affiliations do not have significant moderating effect on the relationship between Facebook content and electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

This subsection describes the concepts that make up the dependent, independent and moderating variables in the study and their relationships. The dependent variable is the electorate's political behaviour while Facebook content and group affiliation were the independent and moderating variable respectively.

Electorates Political Behaviour

This refers to actions and attitudes related to politics, including voting, participation in political discussions, and engagement with political campaigns (Verba et al., 1995). It encompasses the various actions, attitudes, and decision-making processes that individuals undertake when participating in electoral processes. It is a complex field within political science, providing insights into why and how people vote. Political behaviour refers to the act of casting a vote in an election, including the choice of candidate or party. Political behaviour may be characterized by the motivations that drive individuals to participate in elections, such as issues, values, or party affiliation. Political behaviour can

be analyzed through patterns of voter turnout across different demographics and regions, shedding light on disparities in participation.

The significance of understanding political behaviour cannot be overstated. Voter behavior influences policy outcomes, as elected officials respond to the preferences and demands of their constituents. Studying voter behaviour helps hold elected officials accountable for their actions, as it reveals what voters prioritize and expect from their representatives. Parties adapt their strategies based on political behaviour insights to maximize their electoral success, such as crafting campaign messages and platforms.

Research on political behaviour contributes to our understanding of democratic processes, enabling the refinement of electoral systems and voter education initiatives. Political behaviour research informs civic education efforts, helping to equip citizens with the knowledge and critical thinking skills needed to make informed voting decisions.

Political behaviour is highly diverse, with individual choices shaped by a wide range of factors, including values, interests, and circumstances. Political behaviour can be volatile, as political events, campaign dynamics, and candidates' performances can influence election outcomes. Political behaviour often exhibits demographic patterns, with differences in voting behaviour based on age, education, race, and other factors.

Many voters engage in issue-based voting, prioritizing specific policy areas that align with their values or concerns. In some elections, voter behaviour may be more candidate-centric, driven by the personal attributes and qualities of the candidates.

Globally, particularly in the United Kingdom, voter behaviour varies in different types of elections, with factors such as Brexit, party dynamics, and regional variations influencing voting decisions. In the United States, voter behaviour is influenced by factors like party affiliation, ideology, and the specific issues or personalities in each election.

In Europe, particularly in Germany, voter behaviour is characterized by high voters' turnout and the influence of party loyalty, as the political landscape is anchored by established parties. In Italy, the country has continually experienced shifts in voter behaviour due to the country's multi-party system and evolving political coalitions.

In Africa, especially in South Africa and Ghana, political behaviour varies widely due to diverse political landscapes, historical contexts, and levels of democracy. In Nigeria, the nation grapples with issues of political behaviour related to the role of ethnicity, religion, and regionalism in electoral choices.

Political behaviour is influenced by factors like party identification, candidate appeal, issue salience, campaign messages, media exposure, and individual characteristics. Voter behaviour has implications for the composition of legislative bodies, the selection of leaders, and the direction of public policy.

Political behaviour research informs political campaigns, party strategies, and voter education initiatives, fostering a more informed and engaged electorate. It contributes to a deeper understanding of democratic processes and can help enhance the representativeness and accountability of democratic systems.

Social Media

Social Media can be defined as online resources that people use to share content such as videos, photos, images, text, ideas, insight, and opinions (Janusz, 2019). Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) define social media as a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of web 2.0, which allows the creation and exchange of user-generated content. According to Acar and Polonsky (2017), social media sites allow users to participate in social media promoting the contribution and feedback from the users who are interested in participating while social media channels are open for comments no matter what the opinion. The conversation is the basis for developing a community and that is what social media channels provide, open communication.

The Associated Press (AP) Stylebook (2013) defines Social media as online tools that people use to connect with one another including social networks. Adibe, Odoemela and Orji (2012) describe social media as online content created by people using highly accessible and scalable publishing technologies to disseminate information across geographical boundaries, providing interaction among people. Carr and Hayes (2015) define social media as internet-based channels that allow users to opportunistically interact and selectively self-present, either in real-time or asynchronously, with both broad and narrow audiences to derive value from user-generated content and the perception of interaction with others.

Communication Expert Joseph Thornley (2008) defines social media as online communications in which individuals shift fluidly and flexibly between the role of audience and author. To do this, they use social software that enables anyone without knowledge of coding, to post comment on, share or mash up content and to form communities around shared interests. Simply put, social media is an umbrella term used to describe the various types of internet-based applications that lend themselves to content creation sharing, exchange, collaboration and social networking within a website.

Although social media platforms can be accessed via the web (e.g. desktop computers, and laptops) they are mainly accessed via mobile devices like cell phones, tablets, and iPods. According to Facebook's 3rd quarter (2015) report, over 70% percent of total Facebook active users access it through mobile devices. The numbers are growing for Facebook and it's from mobile. To bring it home, the same Facebook report reveals that 15 million Nigerians access the website via mobile devices monthly. In essence, the compatibility of social media with mobile internet is a key advantage which dovetails neatly with the ever-mobile lifestyle of the youth and working-class adults.

Facebook Content and Political Behaviour

Facebook is a social networking site that was created by Mark Zuckerberg in 2004 while he was a student at Harvard University. It was initially restricted to Harvard students only but was later extended to include other Universities/Colleges and then later high schools in the U.S. (Sivadas, Grewal, & Kellaris, 2018).

The popularity of Facebook became worldwide and it was eventually opened up to anyone with an email address to join and create a profile. Facebook has grown at an astronomical rate from its humble beginning as a Harvard campus networking site to a global internet giant boasting a whopping 1.5 billion active users, making it the biggest social networking site in the world. To put it in other words, if Facebook were a country it would be the most populous country in the world (Yang, et al, 2018).

Facebook thus, functions as an online application to see and to be seen: producing and consuming at the same time (Palmer & Koenig-Lewis, 2019). Facebook connects individuals or organizations with their customers or the public by allowing them to see each other's profile pages and by adding their activities to one another's news feeds.

Facebook is the most preferred social network among social media tools as it has more users than any other social network and it is used throughout the world (Ridings, Gefen, & Arinze, 2018). Facebook is not only aimed towards end users but also provides useful tools to organizations, such as groups and pages, advertising, improving customer relationships, and announcing campaigns. Facebook pages are especially effective in communicating with customers directly (Shankar & Malthouse, 2017).

Facebook's monthly active users are 1.23 billion and these numbers include 945 million mobile users and 757 million daily active users; 61% of the users log in to the site every day again, and 77% of the users log in using mobile devices (Acar & Polonsky, 2017). Companies and brands are creating Facebook accounts to share information about themselves, their activities and their campaigns. According to a research conducted in 2009 in USA, 72% of women are learning about a new product or brand from social media, 50% are buying such products, and 67% are commenting about them on social media (Imbens & Rubin, 2015). In Turkey, Facebook had monthly active users of 33 million in December 2013; daily active users were 21 million, mobile monthly active users were 23 million while mobile daily active users were 12 million; 94% of the online population of Turkey is using Facebook, 58% of the online population logs in Facebook every day (Glavas, 2017). It can be said that the reason behind Facebook reaching people in the whole world is its interactivity and the variety of this interactivity (Glavas, 2017).

Facebook communities where users are members are the most relevant for marketers, through these communities, marketers are able to identify consumer tastes and likes, which is essential in helping to create market segmentation targeting and positioning strategies (Acar & Polonsky, 2017). Marketers can gain valuable information from community members' profiles and from the news feed statements that users post on their

walls and pages; this information can then be used for direct marketing purposes (Casteleyn, Mottart, & Rutten, 2019).

According to Edelman (2007), customers are currently switching to the usage of social networks and are spending much more time with online marketing than with any other marketing channel. Facebook allows companies to connect with many more people and much more often than the companies would be able to approach through phone calls, emails, or meetings (Luke, 2009). One of the main benefits of social networking for organizations is, therefore, lower marketing costs in terms of monetary and personnel. With the economic downturn, many companies are trying to find ways to cut spending, and social networking sites are the way for them to market their businesses and reduce their costs. Costs of communication have fallen drastically with Facebook and other social networking sites, creating opportunities for organizations to communicate directly, quickly and consistently with millions of individual customers (Palmer & Koenig-Lewis, 2009).

Moreover, the emergence of Facebook as a marketing platform has ushered in a new era of personalized and directed advertising. Facebook advertising has consequently grown in popularity. Yang et al. (2008) reported that the advent of targeting ads, specifically toward demographics (age, sex, education, and so on), and tighter restrictions on ad quality has turned Facebook advertising into a viable traffic builder and advertising option for small and large size businesses. Because of its sheer number of active users as well as the level of each user's activity on this social networking website, Facebook is considered an appealing platform for Internet marketing specialists and online advertisers (Francisco, 2006). From an economic point of view, Facebook offers a thorough and competitive tariff system, charging advertisers for a per-click or a per-impression model.

Studies have investigated the link between the interaction component of marketing using social networks and the subsequent purchase of products and services. Shankar and Malthouse (2007) found that some relationships reported that marketing firms are increasingly looking to the conversations occurring online to customize their interactions with the customer. Sivadas, Grewal and Killaris (1998) for example, identified a link between online music newsgroup readership and the consumption of music-related products and services such as concerts and recorded music.

Facebook is one of the largest social media platforms, with a broad user base, making it highly relevant in elections. Stier and Bleier (2018) aver that political campaigns use Facebook to reach and engage with voters through targeted advertising, posts, and live streams. Facebook is a key platform for political advertising, allowing campaigns to micro-target specific demographics. Candidates and political parties use Facebook to disseminate campaign materials, share policy positions, and provide updates on campaign activities. Political candidates create Facebook groups and pages to build communities, engage with supporters, and mobilize volunteers (Stier & Bleier, 2018). Research suggests that social media use, including Facebook, can influence political behavior (Gil de Zúñiga et al., 2012).

Group Affiliation and Political Behaviour

Group affiliation refers to membership or identification with a particular group, such as a political party, ethnic group, or interest group (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Group membership is thought to encourage political engagement through a number of mechanisms. First, group membership can provide an opportunity for members to discuss politics. Discussion is thought to be integral to feelings of efficacy among citizens, leading to higher rates of political activity (Andersen & Hansen, 2007; Cho et al., 2009; Delli Carpini, Cook, & Jacobs, 2004; Delli Carpini & Keeter, 1997; Fishkin, 1991; Gastil & Dillard, 1999; Robinson & Levy, 1986). Discussion in a group setting can also promote learning by necessitating the expression of views (Taber & Lodge, 2006) and forcing more thoughtful consideration of viewpoints (Eveland, 2004; Huckfeldt, 2007). Benhabib (1994, p. 30–31) notes that, “when presenting their point of view and position to others, individuals must support them by articulating good reasons in a public context to their co-deliberators. This process of articulating good reasons in public forces the individual to think of what would count as a good reason for all others involved.” Eveland (2004) finds that anticipation of discussion that is counter to one’s own viewpoint motivates individuals to become more informed and elaborate on their own opinions. Reasoning, in this general sense, promotes learning (Cho et al., 2009).

However, deliberation effects are precarious. Studies have found the diversity of discussion to be imperative to knowledge gains, whereas homogenous discussion or one-sided arguments are detrimental to knowledge gains. This is especially evident in the framing literature, which finds that the availability of counter-arguments limits framing effects (Druckman & Chong, 2007; Druckman & Nelson, 2003; Sniderman & Theriault, 2003). Diverse discussion is important in helping people to develop skills that encourage deeper understanding, yet message exposure is only as varied as a person’s network (Gastil, Deess, & Weisler, 2002; Nisbet & Scheufele, 2004; Scheufele, 2002).

When most people discuss politics, “their conversations usually take place within primary groups of family and close friends – that is, among like-minded people who largely resemble each other socially and politically” (Price & Capella, 2002, p. 304; see also Wyatt, Katz, & Kim, 2000).

Group affiliation can moderate this relationship, shaping how individuals respond to Facebook contents and engage in political behavior (Brewer, 1999). Group affiliation can influence individuals' perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors, including their responses to Facebook contents (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). In the context of Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Election, group affiliation may play a significant role in shaping electorates' political behavior.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study is grounded in several theories that explain the relationship between Facebook contents, group affiliation, and electorates' political behavior.

- 1. Social Identity Theory (SIT):** SIT posits that individuals derive a sense of belonging and identity from their group memberships (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). This theory can help explain how group affiliation influences electorates' responses to Facebook contents.
- 2. Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT):** UGT suggests that individuals use social media to satisfy specific needs, such as information seeking or social interaction (Katz et al., 1974). This theory can help understand why electorates engage with Facebook contents.
- 3. Agenda-Setting Theory:** Agenda-setting theory posits that media, including social media, can influence public discourse and shape political agendas (McCombs & Shaw, 1972). This theory can help explain how Facebook contents influence electorates' political behavior.
- 4. Social Capital Theory:** Social capital theory explores how social relationships and networks, including those formed on social media, can facilitate collective action and civic engagement (Putnam, 2000). This theory can help understand the role of Facebook in shaping electorates' political behavior.

2.3 Empirical Review

Shehzad, Yousaf, Mahmood, & Emenyeonu (2021) investigated the impact of Facebook usage on political participation among women in Pakistan. The study employed a cross-sectional research design that surveyed 563 females aged 18 to 60. The findings of the study indicated that online political participation influenced offline political involvement among Pakistani women. It was further found that the purpose of Facebook usage also correlated with online political participation.

Sajid, Javed, and Warraich (2024) in their study titled: The Role of Facebook in Shaping Voting Behavior of Youth: Perspective of a Developing Country explored Facebook's role in shaping the political perception of youth during the 2018 general elections in Pakistan. It was a quantitative study based on a questionnaire survey of young Pakistani voters. Findings show that Facebook has presumed the role of an instigator in shaping the voting behavior of educated youth. Respondents perceived Facebook as biased while expressing views and assisted political entities in manipulating the data to increase their vote bank. Though the majority of them haven't experienced fake news so either they are not conscious or they trust blindly the information. Furthermore, respondents' cognitive abilities are not obstructed by politicians using Facebook, instead, friends and family network seems more persuasive in determining voters' choice. Results manifest that ideological standpoint impacts voters' decisions substantially.

Riezebos, de Vries and Zeeuw (2011) carried out a study on The effects of social media on political party perception and voting behaviour. This study sought to determine to what extent and political voting behaviour. Based on the literature a conceptual model was developed that measures political interest, political trust, religion and the use of social media and their effects on PPP and voting behaviour. Using an online questionnaire the

conceptual model was tested towards and during the Dutch national elections of 2010. Results showed that there are several significant effects on PPP, voting behaviour is solely determined by political interest.

Aslana, Karakoçb, and Bekiroğluc (2021) carried out a study on “The Effect of Social Media on Voter Behavior: The Sample of Kayseri Province.” The study aimed to reveal the effect of social media on voter behaviour, a survey application was conducted with 1231 people in the province of Kayseri. Study results showed that the effect of social media on the voters differed significantly according to gender, marital status, age, education and income status, residence, purpose of use and relevance to the political agenda.

Hussain, Iqbal and Abbasi (2021) carried out a study on the Impact of Social Media on Voting Behavior of Youth during Pakistan General Elections-2018. The objective of the study was to find out the impact of social media on the voting behaviour of youth in general elections (2018) in Pakistan. This research is based on primary data collected from 300 students of various universities of the Federal Capital Territory Islamabad. Through the purposive sampling technique, the university students were selected for the administration of the questionnaire and collection of data on the variables of the study. Regression analysis of the data showed that social media has an impact on the voting behaviour of youth. The results also proved that political activities and political content on social media have the power to influence the voting behaviour of youth.

In another study, Ferrer (2021) carry out a study on “Effects of Social Media on Youth Voter Engagement.” The aim of the study was to find out whether social media can mobilize youth to vote. The study utilized a descriptive survey design and primary data was used to obtain data from respondents. Regression analysis was used to analyze the data obtained. The study results showed that social media has a greater effect on youth than it does on older age groups and outreach efforts conducted on social media seem to be successful.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional research design and survey method of data collection. The study covers the six geo-political zones in Nigeria in order to create a proper representation for the whole country. The following states were chosen to cover for each of the geo-political zones in Nigeria: Enugu for South-East (SE), River State for South-South (SS), FCT Abuja for North-Central (NC), Lagos State for South-West (SW), Gombe State for North-East (NE), and Kano State for North-West (NW).

The population of the study comprised of residence of these states as at the time of the elections. Given the area of this study, the study population was made up of 21,777,649 people of voting age who are eligible to participate in the electoral process. Given that the total population of this study is known, the researchers applied the Taro Yamane formula for finite sample size in determining the sample size for the study. 400 electorates were

the sample size for the study. Stratified sampling technique was used in this research because it involves dividing the population into sub-populations that may differ in important ways. Bowle's proportional allocation formula was used to allocate the sample proportionally among the selected sample fractions.

The research instrument used in collecting data for this study was questionnaire. This was structured in five-point Likert-style rating scale, ranging from strongly agreed (5) to strongly disagreed (1) with a middle point (3) indicating undecided. The variables were measured thus: Facebook use - Frequency, duration, and type of Facebook use; Group affiliation - Membership or identification with specific groups; Political behaviour - Voting behavior, political participation, and engagement. The questionnaire was created as an online survey using Google form. To reach out to the respondents, the researcher used social media (Facebook messenger and WhatsApp) and e-mail to send out the link for the survey instrument. Mostly, church, community and association group pages were used. The group administrators were personally contacted and the nature and purpose of the survey clearly explained to them. These administrators granted the researcher the opportunity to address the members of the groups and solicit their support in filing the questionnaire.

A pilot survey was conducted by the researchers to determine the appropriateness of the research instrument and its understanding by the study population. The researcher administered a total of 40 copies of the questionnaire to the sample respondents in one of the selected states to pretest the questionnaire and enable the performance of validity and reliability tests.

The validity of this study's instrument was conducted through face validity by research experts. They scrutinized the instrument to ensure that its content measures what the overall study is all about. Corrections and adjustments were made accordingly. To assess the reliability of the research instrument, the researchers adopted the Cronbach's alpha reliability test. The alpha values obtain from the test were greater than 0.7, hence indicating that the construct adopted in this study had internal consistency and good reliability (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016)

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study aims to provide insights into the moderating role of group affiliation on the relationship between Facebook contents and electorates' political behaviour in Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Election. The data collected were analyzed using inferential statistics (the regression analysis) to test the formulated hypotheses and examine relationships between variables. The hypotheses were tested at a 5% level of significance. The tests were conducted in two stages. The first stage tested the direct effect of the Facebook contents (independent variable) on the electorate's political behaviour (dependent variable) while the second stage tested the moderation effect of group affiliation on the relationship between Facebook contents and the electorate's political behaviour.

Hypothesis One: Facebook content has no significant effect on the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.542 ^a	.294	.292	.86110

a. Predictors: (Constant), FACEBOOK

The model summary of this test indicates that there is a high and positive correlation between Facebook content and electorates' political behaviour ($R = 0.542$). Also, the $R^2 = 0.294$ indicates that 29.4% variation in the dependent variable (electorates political behaviour) was explained by the independent variable (Facebook contents).

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	122.953	1	122.953	165.820	.000 ^b
	Residual	295.853	399	.741		
	Total	418.806	400			

a. Dependent Variable: EPB
b. Predictors: (Constant), FACEBOOK

The ANOVA result which shows that $F=165.820$; $P=0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that Facebook contents is a statistically significant predictor of electorates political behaviour in Nigeria.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.240	.141		8.822	.000
	FACEBOOK	.518	.040	.542	12.877	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EPB

The test result shows that Facebook content with coefficient values of ($\beta=0.518$; $t=12.877$; $p=0.000 < 0.05$) indicates that one percent increase in Facebook content effects 51.8% positive change on electorates' political behaviour. This implies that Facebook content is a statistically significant predictor of electorates' political behaviour. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis which states that "Facebook content has no significant effect on the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria". Hence, Facebook content significantly and positively affect the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: Group affiliations do not have significant moderating effect on the relationship between Facebook content and electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.683 ^a	.467	.465	.74814

a. Predictors: (Constant), GA_FACEBOOK

The model summary of this test indicates that there is a high and positive correlation between the moderated effect of group affiliation on Facebook contents and electorates political behaviour ($R = 0.683$). Also, the $R^2 = 0.467$ indicates that 46.7% variation in the dependent variable (electorates political behaviour) was explained by the moderated effect of group affiliation on Facebook contents.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	195.482	1	195.482	349.255	.000 ^b
	Residual	223.324	399	.560		
	Total	418.806	400			
a. Dependent Variable: EPB						
b. Predictors: (Constant), GA_FACEBOOK						

The ANOVA result which shows that $F=349.255$; $P=0.000<0.05$ indicates that the moderated effect of group affiliation on Facebook contents is a statistically significant predictor of electorates' political behaviour in Nigeria.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.624	.081		20.069	.000
	GA_FACEBOOK	.116	.006	.683	18.688	.000
a. Dependent Variable: EPB						

The test result shows that moderated effect of group affiliation on Facebook content with coefficient values of ($\beta=0.116$; $t=18.688$; $p=0.000<0.05$) indicates that the moderated effect of group affiliation on Facebook content is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis which states that, "Group affiliations do not have significant moderating effect on the relationship between Facebook content and electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria". Hence, Group affiliations have significant moderating effect on the relationship between Facebook content and electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first specific objective aims to determine the extent to which Facebook content influence the electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria. The study's findings indicate that Facebook contents significantly and positively influenced electorates' political behaviour in Nigeria's 2023 Presidential Election.

This implies that under a normal circumstance, political contents posted through Facebook have a direct positive effect on political education, participation, and believability of political messages. This finding is consistent with previous research. These include Adoyi, et al. (2022), Halpern, Valenzuela and Katz (2017), Nyitse, Terhile and Clayton (2020), Gil de Zúñiga et al. (2012), and Bond et al. (2012).

The second specific objective aims to determine the extent to which Group affiliations have moderating effect on the relationship between Facebook content and electorates' political behaviour during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

The result shows that moderating role of group affiliation was significant, suggesting that individuals' group identities shaped their responses to Facebook contents and political behavior. It means that if groups that one is affiliated to hold an opinion contrary to that which is popularized on Facebook, the effects it supposed to create on the electorates will be significantly reduced.

This explains why there were so many contents on Facebook about the elections but the behaviour of the electorates didn't reflect it. This is in line with the finding of Uwalaka (2021) which shows that protest experience and political efficacy significantly increased students' intention to join politics more than social media. The result also align with those of Tajfel and Turner (1979); and Brewer (1999).

These findings have implications for understanding the complex dynamics of social media, group identity, and political behavior in Nigeria's democratic process. They suggest that politicians and campaign managers should consider the role of group affiliation when developing social media strategies (Gerodimos & Justinussen, 2015).

Contribution to Knowledge

The study contributes to understanding the complex dynamics of social media, group affiliation, and political behavior in Nigeria's democratic process. The findings and recommendations can inform strategies for effective political communication and engagement through social media.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends:

1. Political actors: Tailor Facebook contents to specific group affiliations to effectively engage electorates.
2. Electorates: Critically evaluate Facebook contents and consider multiple sources of information.
3. Policymakers: Develop guidelines for responsible social media use in politics.
4. Future research: Explore the impact of other social media platforms on political behavior.

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research:

The study's limitations include its focus on Facebook and the 2023 Presidential Election in Nigeria. Future research should explore other social media platforms and electoral contexts. Future studies should investigate the impact of other moderating variables, such as age, gender, and socioeconomic status, on the relationship between social media use and political behavior.

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